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POPE FRANCIS AND THE ENVIRONMENT: CONTRIBUTIONS?

AUTHOR

Antonio Augusto Dornelas de Andrade (antonioandradepey@gmail.com): Holds a Master's Degree and a PhD in Educational Sciences from Columbia University in Paraguay; a Bachelor's Degree in Theology from the Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro-RJ; a Degree in History from the Faveni University Center, Guarulhos-SP; He has a degree in Philosophy from the Catholic Faculty of Anápolis-G0; he is a Specialist in Afro-Indigenous Brazilian Culture from UNINTER - Centro Universitário Internacional, Curitiba-SP; he is a Specialist in Tutoring and Distance Education from Faculdades Jardins, Aracaju-SE. He is a regular priest in the Archdiocese of Rio de Janeiro.

ABSTRACT

The theme of this paper is "Pope Francis and the Environment: Contributions?". It is an article formulated using the integrative literature review method, which seeks, through the sources that are cited throughout, to list how the writings published by Pope Francis, including his encyclical, manage to have an impact within the context of the climate and environmental crisis that is being faced across the planet. In order to make this point, in its introductory section, the article initially presents a general reflection on the proposed theme, explaining the objectives it aims to achieve. In its development, it seeks to initially show the pragmatic nature of Pope Francis' writings and their relationship or usability within the corporate world, then evaluates the same factors, this time in the political world, seeking to establish a connection between the practical nature of these writings and their essentiality in all contexts, which cannot be considered as purely religious manifestations, since they reflect theoretically and critically on real problems of the entire global community. In its final section, the article brings reflections and understandings that ratify the idea worked on throughout its development and reflect on the real contributions of Pope Francis' writings to discussion, understanding and pointing out solutions to the problems related to global warming.

KEYWORDS: Climate Crisis. Water Crisis. Writings. Pope Francis.

INTRODUCTION

The search for ways to find a minimally plausible solution to the problems that make up the whole context of global warming has been recurrent in the political and corporate context. Entities such as the United Nations (UN) and the World Health Organization (WHO), as well as governments and various groups, are seeking solutions so that life on planet Earth can continue to exist.

This, however, had not been the pursuit of religious entities. In fact, among the many religious denominations on the planet, there is a certain lack of interest in scientific matters, which are left to convert their faithful and to pursue a quest aimed at the zeal and preservation of their traditions.

This context, however, has changed significantly with the stance adopted by Pope Francis, who in the publication of his encyclical made clear his concern about the environmental problems facing the planet, showing with the publication of this thought - which is a disruptive thought and aware of the problems afflicting the community - that the church can continue with its dogmas, models of thought and defense of its traditions, while helping in a practical way to contribute to the resolution of a problem that affects everyone.

With this in mind, the general aim of this article is to evaluate the contributions of Pope Francis' writings as a means of tackling the climate crisis and the water crisis. Specifically, the aim is to find out what impacts the stance adopted by the Pope has had within the political and corporate sectors, while also reflecting on the importance of the Church's position in relation to global problems that are already a reality affecting a considerable number of people. According to Capra (2020), without collaboration, all the problems arising from the climate crisis and global warming as a whole will affect the global community in such a way that their impacts become irreversible. In this sense, the author states that the Pope's theoretical contribution through his writings is coherent and highly contributory, highlighting its relevance and essentiality for everyone.

The choice of this theme is based on the understanding that Pope Francis' stance, clearly stated in his writings, points to a path of reflection,

in which a change in everyone's behavior should be taken as a starting point for global awareness, which is indispensable for tackling the climate problems that are getting worse every day.

DEVELOPMENT

Throughout this article, we will discuss the practical nature of Pope Francis' writings, trying to correlate them with the current corporate context, pointing out the synergy between what the Pope wrote and the dynamics adopted by large companies and international entities. Next, the environmental discourse present in Pope Francis' writings and its relationship with the political scene is evaluated, also in accordance with the sources. Both topics seek to point out the relevance and essentiality of the Pope's discourse, observing how his stance contributes to the scenario of preservation, sustainability and conscious consumption that we want to propagate in global society.

THE PRACTICAL NATURE OF POPE FRANCIS' WRITINGS AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE CORPORATE WORLD

According to Oliveira (2016), building a world along the ideal lines that ensure the continuity of life on earth involves a growing evaluation of models and interactions that focus on the general perception that everyone's conduct is relevant and that no one should not be held responsible for their actions. The author goes on to point out that the context of preservation, social responsibility, commitment to the environment, conscious consumption and care for natural resources are factors that need to occur both in the collective and the individual context.

In general terms, what is absorbed is the understanding that, within the need for preservation, care and commitment that is being carried out across the globe, there is an implicit understanding that without everyone's contribution, it will not be possible to achieve the results that are sought.

In relation to this thought, Boff (2016) is emphatic in reiterating the fact that the global population must be made aware of the need to nurture an awareness that the idealized human conduct, which recognizes its responsibility to care for its own home - in this

case the planet on which everyone lives - must be motivated in a systemic and uninterrupted way.

Based on the recognition that it is everyone's duty to take care of the environment in which they live and to look after the resources that are the key to life on earth continuing, it is recognized that it is minimally prudent to have as a source of recognition, the perception that studies and writings that ratify such conduct should be evaluated and validated, recognizing in them an opportunity to corroborate the process of awareness, so necessary for the preservation of the planet.

Thus, according to Nobre and Conceição (2021), if we take Pope Francis' many writings as a basis, what we see is an alignment of the Catholic Church representative's thinking on the need to make the faithful aware of their responsibility in the process of caring for and preserving planet Earth as their home, and the resources present on it, as a means of continuing life on this planet.

In Lima's view (2015), the assessment of Pope Francis' writings points to a stance that is unique from a social, humanitarian, religious and statistical point of view. From a social point of view, it is clear that by showing his position and alignment with the problems and demands that are urgently needed to be discussed, the Pope shows his knowledge of the real condition of the planet, with regard to factors such as the climate crisis, the environmental crisis and the water crisis. In the humanitarian context, the Holy Father's thinking aims to show that there are already people suffering the consequences of these problems and that, therefore, everyone's action must be urgent. From a religious and statistical point of view, the Pope's alignment is pertinent, focusing on the process of raising awareness and converting as many of the sheep in his flock as possible, in order to gather ideas, strength and resources so that these problems can be tackled in practice.

According to Reis and Bizawu (2015), we need to understand that the apocalyptic reality that is constantly being propagated by scientists is no longer a subjective or distant factor. The reality of the climate crisis is knocking on everyone's

door and its impacts are already hitting everyone hard. The recurring search by large corporations for greater sustainability, the reuse of essential resources such as water, reforestation and the use of clean energy sources are factors that show that, without the adoption of more conscious and responsible measures, the result will be catastrophes that will make life on the planet more impossible every day.

In this context, Júnior (2018) makes it clear that it is already certain within the corporate world that actions carried out by companies aimed solely at profit, without any concern for the planet or conscious use, should be extinguished. This stance of condemning actions aimed at profit without any benefit being generated for the planet has become increasingly recurrent, and has had a great power to raise awareness.

Alves (2017), when dealing with this topic, makes it clear that unregulated consumption has been the target of constant criticism, due to the fact that consumers in general have - albeit slowly - come to understand that companies that are more environmentally responsible should be prioritized when choosing which brand or product to consume. Part of this understanding, according to Alves (2017), comes from the recognition that the responsibility for looking after the planet belongs to everyone, and for this reason, the author cites the potential impact of writings such as those of Pope Francis with regard to a process of awareness that is increasingly necessary within the community as a whole.

According to Pinhal (2017), for a long time, people in general were led to believe that their role in a truly relevant and efficient preservation model to save the planet was dispensable. It was commonly believed that only actions carried out on a large scale and with high investment power by large companies and conglomerates would make a difference to the conservation of various natural resources.

Over time, this thinking has been diluted and given way to the realization that everyone's care and awareness of their role in preserving the planet must be constant and adjusted in order to

validate an increasingly active stance on the part of everyone.

For this reason, Oliveira and Lima (2020) cite Pope Francis' encyclical, for example, as a model of theoretical contribution, capable of integrating the Pope's knowledge of the cause in relation to global warming, correlating the need for everyone to play a leading role - including the faithful of the Catholic Church - as an essential point within the care that must be taken for the planet. This makes sense of the idea that not raising awareness, not reiterating to members of the Catholic Church the importance of everyone's participation in the process of preserving the planet, is to incur in the systematic production of a legion of alienated people who

will row against the flow of preservation, believing it to be a certain and apocalyptic fate, devaluing the idea that the climate crisis is actually a problem that stems from the misuse of natural resources by human beings, and from heinous actions such as deforestation, the unregulated use of resources such as water and, above all, the lack of commitment on the part of everyone to the zeal that must be shown for the common home that we all inhabit, the planet.

In this regard, Zamperi (2016) points to the Pope's position in his encyclical as essential. Throughout his thesis, the author reiterates the understanding that the conscious participation of a religious entity like the Catholic Church fosters the perception that the preservation of the planet is not focused on an insane struggle between science and religion.

To this end, Macedo (2015) makes it clear that by talking about the climate crisis in his encyclical, as well as other factors such as the water crisis, the extinction of animal species and the need to take a more responsible stance on the environment in which we live, Pope Francis ends up ratifying the understanding that the fuss that scientists from all over the planet have been making for decades has long since left the subjective plane and entered the practical social context.

Siqueira (2016), when dealing with this issue,

makes it clear that Pope Francis' stance shows that the adoption of measures and adjustments to business models as a result of global warming by large corporations is aimed at carrying out actions that validate a preservation approach that has become increasingly recurrent within the current social model.

For this reason, Tavares (2016) explains that by showing his understanding of the environmental problems affecting the planet, the Pope manages to overturn the false idea that the adjustment in business models, and the changes brought about for large corporations, from the structural adjustment of their foundations, to the eminent need to adopt cleaner and more sustainable energy sources, cannot be treated as moves to attract more consumers, it is simply a quest that aims to preserve planet Earth as a habitable place for all the species that live on it.

Thus, when evaluating what is exposed in Viana (2019), what we have is the perception that the synergy between the scientific discourse on the need for everyone to change their habits, the adoption of more humanistic and responsible attitudes by large corporations and the idea defended by the Pope, point to the need for more commitment and responsibility on the part of everyone who lives on this planet, whether they are Catholics or not.

THE ENVIRONMENTAL DISCOURSE IN THE WRITINGS OF POPE FRANCIS AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH THE POLITICAL ARENA

Boff (2016), when dealing with the formation of modern society, is assertive in saying that the political scene as a whole has managed to establish itself in a secular condition that can skillfully separate the religious plot from the political plot. In the author's perception, this condition has meant that religious thinking has been considered increasingly retrograde and incompatible with social demands and problems.

This perception of the aforementioned author refers to the common sense that fails to recognize

that the position of religious entities such as the Catholic Church has long since migrated to the present. In this way, it is emphatic to mention, as Boff (2016) himself points out, that respect for traditions does not make a church old-fashioned; on the contrary, it only ratifies the relevance of its beliefs as it connects with the present and adapts to the social requirements and needs present in each community.

For Nobre and Conceição (2021), it is coherent to understand that the quest to separate politics and religion has been a constant in the process of world evolution, however, there have been few results that indicate success in this quest. The authors reiterate that the Catholic Church has been one of the few entities that has remained faithful to the understanding that the scopes of politics and religion are somewhat distinct.

Even so, it is clear that politics, unlike religion, is present in all scenarios, and the impact of the decisions made by various leaders directly affects everyone, which is why it is important to always pay attention to the measures that are taken within the political sphere. In this case, it is also necessary to point out the fact that the way politics is done has changed considerably and this has made it possible for everyone to participate, thus making the democratic precept of the regime in which we live valid.

In this way, it is recognized that the act of doing politics, of manifesting oneself politically, has a direct relationship with the exercise of citizenship that is incumbent on everyone. Therefore, when a Christian expresses himself politically, he is not in a condition of politicking, but rather in full exercise of his duty as a citizen, as a person able to contribute either practically, cognitively or critically to the world in which he lives.

According to Oliveira (2016), the position presented by the Pope in his theoretical contributions has to do with the exercise of citizenship and responsibility that belongs to each person in this context of the global climate crisis. In general, it is possible to see that his contribution has more to do with each person's inherent need to efficiently and responsibly build a social model

that is coherent with combating the crisis that is already a reality in everyone's life.

According to Reis and Bizawu (2015), the political content of the papal writings has a deep connection with a more humanist and self-responsible stance that needs to be defended and supported by everyone. In this case, the authors reinforce the idea that the climate crisis, the decline and extinction of species is a struggle that must be fought by everyone. Building a world in which these problems that are already afflicting humanity now must be done by everyone and not outsourced to corporate or political groups.

According to Alves (2017), it is important that each person has the ability to question their contribution to combating climate problems, recognizing that without everyone involved in combating this problem, the result will be a dead planet, with no possibility of allowing humanity to continue living on it.

In line with the understanding shown above, Lima (2015) points out that this is no longer a fight for which governments have to fight. When assessing the impacts of climate change on the entire planet in a practical way, it is pertinent to constantly reiterate that the responsibility for taking care of the planet belongs to everyone.

It is this thought that Pope Francis adopts in his writings, that of making everyone reflect on the urgency of these problems, while also emphasizing the importance of having defended the fact that everyone is responsible for taking care of the planet as their common home. In this context, Macedo (2015) emphasizes the fact that undoubtedly the greatest legacy present in Pope Francis' writings is precisely the awareness of his faithful about the situation facing the entire planet.

The author goes on to say that raising awareness among the population has been one of the great taboos in this struggle, given that in many cases there is disbelief about the situation of the planet and in others there is the bizarre claim that this condition is predictable because it is part of God's will.

Pinhal (2017) evaluates a stance that highlights

the fact that, in showing concern about the calamitous scenario in which we live, Pope Francis adopts a stance that is loaded with a good dose of pragmatism, making it clear that the problem of global warming is actually a consequence of human inconsideration that has adopted a predatory stance over centuries and has insistently invested in unregulated growth and progress at any cost.

This acknowledgement is actually a highly conscious explanation of how human beings have been detrimental to the development of the planet and, in a way, breaks with blaming entities, governments and even the divine will, so as not to have to admit that the condition we are facing now is the responsibility of everyone who lives here.

For Siqueira (2016), by recognizing the need for awareness, a change in attitude and a conduct that needs to be adopted by everyone in favour of the well-being of life on planet Earth, what the Pope has managed to do is provide biblical proof that the predatory conduct adopted until now by human beings is incompatible with the zeal, love, sharing and compassion so defended in the sacred texts.

In this way, Tavares (2016) finds an understanding that points to an idea that efficiently translates the nature of the papal writings in relation to the context of preservation and conscious use of natural resources. In this step, the author reiterates the fact that, contrary to countless biblical versions and interpretations that point to God's will as something perverse, that blames and punishes the guilty for their mistakes and that is totally disinterested in the need to care for and preserve this planet, Pope Francis manages to break with this type of thinking and points out to his faithful the need to care for and preserve what is God's most beautiful gift in everyone's life. This planet.

According to Viana (2019), by showing that his capacity for reflection is connected to the preservation of a scenario that is good and suitable for everyone to experience, the Pope incurs - albeit unintentionally - in a political

conduct. According to Capra (2020), without the collaboration of all the problems arising from the climate crisis and global warming as a whole, they have affected the global community in such a way that their impacts become irreversible. In this sense, the author states that the Pope's theoretical contribution through his writings is coherent and highly contributory, highlighting its relevance and essentiality for everyone.

Zamperi (2016) points out that what is proposed in Pope Francis' writings is not focused on conversion or alienating the people who read it; what is actually proposed is to make everyone aware of a real problem that requires them to adopt a more assertive stance that is coherent with the context in which they live. At this point, the Pope manages to make it clear - especially in his encyclical - that the act of being a Christian does not exempt Catholics from their commitment to caring for the planet.

A similar thought can be found in Oliveira and Lima (2020), when the authors reiterate the fact that the proposal presented by the Pope emphasizes the understanding that the religious stance adopted by a person does not remove from them the responsibility of having to deal with community problems. In this context, the authors point out that political thinking and a stance that is more coherent with the needs and problems present in society only endorse the thesis that religious thinking needs to distance itself from the common sense that points to it as alienating and disconnected from the reality we live in.

Thus, Júnior (2018) understands that the exercise of a political stance by Christians has as its main scope the ratification that religious thought is not limiting, and each person's belief only concerns the need to validate their faith. In this context, the same author reiterates the fact that the contributions present in Pope Francis' writings show that his conduct has political references that reiterate his citizen conduct and that show the importance of being a theoretical model that discusses problems such as the climate crisis and the water crisis with different eyes. Finally, Capra (2020) makes it clear in his understanding that the proposal presented by the Holy Father in his

writings manages to ratify the clear intention of the greatest representative of the Catholic Church, for a problem that belongs to everyone and that needs, in order to be solved, the awareness and contribution of each of the people who inhabit this planet, making it understandable that the constitution of a safe future depends on the way each person decides to act in the now.

CONCLUSION

Pope Francis' theoretical contributions to tackling global problems arising from the climate crisis, which is already a reality for everyone, provide a glimpse of a humanist, critical and conscious view of the impacts that global warming has on everyone. In his theoretical approaches, the Pope adopts a conscious stance that is familiar with other studies and still preserves the religious character of his persona. He provides his readers with an understanding that the scarcity of natural resources such as water, the dynamics of preservation and the adoption of measures such as conscious consumption and the responsible use of natural resources is everyone's responsibility.

In general, the authors cited throughout this study are able to correlate the papal stance with the measures adopted in both the political and corporate spheres, showing that their behavior is aligned with that of government institutions as well as large companies, highlighting the Catholic Church's understanding of factors that are more scientific in nature and also more distant from the religious context as we have seen.

At this point, it is important to remember that Pope Francis has shown himself to be coherent and aware of the measures and attitudes needed within the contemporary model of social interaction, recognizing the potential of the Catholic Church to play a leading role in this quest to save the planet. Looking more deeply into his writings, it can be seen that the Pope seeks through his words to convert his flock to recognize the fact that their stance as Christians is directly related to the preservation of their common home with their other brothers and sisters.

This reflection generates a relevant reflexive

potential, which connects with the search for other corporations and governmental and non-governmental organizations, making the faithful of the Catholic Church recognize themselves as protagonists in the preservation of the planet, becoming aware of the fact that it is not possible to outsource the responsibility that one has in making sure that resources are used consciously, and in recognizing that without adopting a posture of responsibility, care and zeal for the scenario that one has, the end of all is practically certain.

Finally, it is recognized that Pope Francis' contributions to the environmental issue facing the planet reflect an innovative stance that, despite being disruptive in many respects, signals the protagonist identity of the Catholic Church, which has been present in many of the global incursions, such as the great navigations, for example. Before concluding this article, it is important to reiterate the fact that, in adopting a stance that reflects a greater and better environmental awareness, the Pope has not renounced the precepts that qualify him as the representative of the world's largest church.

On the contrary, what has been clearly shown by the Holy Father in the course of his writings is the fact that, by ratifying what is shown in the Bible, it is perfectly possible for the church to continue in full preservation of its values, and also in favor of preserving the world as it is known today, which it also helped to create.

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